

IS ALBER CAMUS EXISTENTIALISM

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Abstract: This article briefly covers the humanitarian ideas of Albert Camus, one of the great representatives of the existentialist philosophy. The article shows that the issue of art occupies a central place in the existentialism of Albert Camus.

Key words: existentialism, humanism, alienation, absurdity, rebellion, revolution, art, beauty, freedom, human rights, meaning of life.

Аннотация: В данной статье кратко рассматриваются гуманитарные идеи Альбера Камю, одного из крупнейших представителей экзистенциалистской философии. В статье показано, что проблема искусства занимает центральное место в экзистенциализме Альбера Камю.

Ключевые слова: экзистенциализм, гуманизм, отчуждение, абсурд, бунт, революция, искусство, красота, свобода, права человека, смысл жизни.

Аннотация: Ушбу мақолада экзистенциализм фалсафасининг йирик вакилларидан бири Альбер Камюнинг инсонпарварлик ғоялари қисқача ёритилган. Мақолада Альбер Камю экзистенциализмида санъат масаласи асосий ўрин тутиши кўрсатиб ўтилган.

Калит сўзлар: экзистенциализм, гуманизм, бегоналашиш, бемаънилиқ, исён, инқилоб, санъат, гўзаллик, эркинлик, инсон ҳуқуқлари, ҳаётнинг маъноси.

Albert Camus (1913-1960) is a French philosopher and writer, one of the representatives of secular existentialism.

As an existentialist-philosopher, Camus traveled the path from nihilistic "absurd philosophy" to moral humanism. Camus, in his early writings, still propagates his own philosophy of paganism. It honors the unity and harmony of man with nature. And it shows that thanks to this unity and interaction, a person develops in all aspects, achieves spiritual integrity, and becomes a real "I". However, he begins to write about the current world as a world of injustice, alienation, doomed to destruction and nonsense. Meursault, the hero of the play, avoids all the dishes of bourgeois society. He puts his mother in the orphanage because she can't take care of him. He looks at his mother's death with indifference. Sitting next to his mother's coffin is boring for him. Meursault is indifferent to all rituals. After his mother's burial, he begins an affair with the

woman he lives with the next day as if nothing had happened. Meursault is also indifferent to this woman. Merson has only a lustful relationship with this woman. After that, he befriends a pimp. In the end, Meursault, for no apparent reason, shoots and kills an Arab man walking by the sea. (This event takes place in Algeria). In court, all his "immoral qualities" will be revealed, and Meursault will be sentenced to death.

Why is Meursault like this and what is the meaning of the path he chose? The meaning of this was Meursault's attempt to communicate with people in a language free from falsehoods and pretenses. But it was not possible to do so. Because language was created only to speak lies and express falsehood. Therefore, he is condemned to stay away from others, keep silent, talk to himself. Camus neither accuses nor acquits the stranger. The philosopher shows that Meursault chose solitude and death in the path of sincerity and self-expression. Thus, Camus believes that in this world, man considers himself a "stranger", and only at the border of death he begins to feel free and happy.

In *The Legend of Sisyphus*, Camus raises the problem of the absurdity of human life and suicide. According to Camus, the problem of suicide is the only real serious problem of philosophy. Solving the question of what is the meaning of life and whether life is worth living is an answer to the fundamental question of philosophy, the philosopher says [1:481].

In this work, Camus tried to describe the life of depressed and suicidal people of his time, referring to the image of Sisyphus in the ancient Greek myth, to show them that life is a great blessing. According to the legend, due to his cunning, Sisyphus was condemned by the Gods to lift a large stone to the top of the mountain. No matter what Sisyphus does, the stone keeps falling down from the top of the mountain. The gods condemned Sisyphus to such a punishment, based on the fact that there is no worse punishment than useless and pointless labor.

Camus first tries to connect suicide with nonsense (absurd). It shows that suicide is, in a certain sense, the result of absurdity. According to Camus, suicide is first prepared in the web of the soul as an individual phenomenon. Secondly, the event that is usually called a reason is actually just an excuse.

Camus approaches the problem of absurdity and suicide more as a psychologist than a philosopher. He writes: "A sense of absurdity awaits us at every corner." This feeling cannot be seen or felt in the dim light of its own atmosphere. This imperceptibility is remarkable." [1:482]. An imperceptible,

hard-to-notice feeling of absurdity can be partially perceived in the consciousness devices necessary for this or that feeling.

Camus raises the issue of human rights and freedoms in "The Rebel". He said that rebellion is the work of a person who is aware of his rights, is aware of everything, and is knowledgeable. Rebellion occurs primarily in societies that are far from good. For people living in subjugated societies, rebellion is one of the important dimensions of their existence. In the process of realizing oneself as a human being, rebellion also appears. According to Camus, rebellion plays the same role in human life as thought does in Descartes' philosophy. ("I think, therefore I exist"). That is, "I am rebelling, therefore I exist." Rebellion and revolution are the fate and fate of modern man, says Camus. Therefore, rebellion as an element of civilization informs any civilization. Because the revolution is introduced in civilizations, not in conditions of tyranny and terror.

Camus sees history as "metaphysical", "historical" and "artistic" types of rebellion. And how can a person exist and retain his humanity? - tries to find an answer to the question. What should a person do to find justice, find truth, inspire confidence in people, and celebrate goodness and beauty? - asks the question. Camus focuses on art to solve these problems. According to him, only art has the ability to express the content and perspective of the rebellion. And the artist has the ability to change the world according to his calculations and perspective. Camus tries to develop new humanist ideas that unite all people and serve to ensure their freedom. The ideal of universal communication should be the ideal of every artist, says the philosopher. Camus, in the spirit of F. M. Dostoevsky, puts forward the rule that beauty saves the world. Beauty does not revolutionize, says Camus, but the day will come when the revolution will need beauty. Camus praises human nature and the beauty of the universe, and denies injustice.

His humanism does not aim to make man completely happy, but to make him conscious, to free him from the metaphysical, moral and political superstitions and falsehoods that surround him, as well as to free him from various dogmas and false ideas. Beauty cannot serve any party, any state. It serves only freedom and love. Beauty and freedom can liberate people from captivity, enrich them meaningfully, morally, emotionally and intellectually, and help them achieve social justice.

Stoic motives are strong in Camus' worldview. It is seen in man's call to revolt against the absurdity of his existence and evil. In later periods, Camus began to understand the concept of rebellion not only as a denial of the

absurdity of existence, but also in the sense of introducing universal values such as freedom, solidarity, love, that is, as phenomena that find expression in art. At the same time, Camus emphasizes the opposition of rebellion and revolution, and therefore art and revolution.

Camus shows that all historical revolutions that established new strict orders were hostile to art. Because art embodies rebellion against all kinds of complexity. In his works, the artist gives unity and form to the world, tries to eliminate its chaos by himself, and tries to find beauty in the vast and ugly world. The beauty created by the artist helps people to love this world.

Analyzing the relationship between art and reality, Camus criticizes formalism for its distance from the world. And at the same time, he accuses realism of being completely obsessed with life. According to Camus, the true style of mature art should be free from these two contradictions and one-sidedness.

Camus emphasizes that there are two forms of protest in the 20th century - revolution and art. Among these, the philosopher gives priority to art, glorifies it. Camus sees in art the real face of rebellion, the eternal creative protest against what has been created up to that time. Camus says that the artist expresses the spirit of the age and the aspirations of the people and is responsible for them. Thus, in his philosophy, Camus calls people to rebel against absurdity. However, Camus's rebellion is a spiritual-spiritual rebellion related to the existence and living of an individual. Camus did not see in society a powerful social force that opposes absurdity and alienation. And that's why everyone showed the need to fight against absurdity and alienation, to build their own life.

References:

1. Камю А. «Миф о Сизифе», «Эссе об абсурде». Хрестоматия по философии: учебное пособие. М. : «Проспект», 1998. Стр.-481.
2. Камю А. «Миф о Сизифе», «Эссе об абсурде». Хрестоматия по философии: учебное пособие. М. : «Проспект», 1998. Стр.-482